

IMPLICATION OF PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP AND MANAGERIAL COMPETENCE OF SCHOOL MANAGERS

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ABSTRACT

This pandemic brought us many experiences and realizations in life. It is very challenging for everyone to adapt to what we called the new normal most specifically are the school heads and teachers in the field of teaching. Even though pandemic stops many establishments, the school is continuously operating, and nothing can hamper this. So, school heads bring up to date their progress to constantly adapt to changes made by the current situation. To support this, this research study is presenting the implication of professional and personal development in the instructional leadership and managerial competence of school managers. The survey questionnaire through the use of google form led to attaining the main objectives of the study partaking by 60 school managers and 131 elementary teachers in this academic year 2020-2021 who are currently employed in twenty-three (23) schools of Sariaya West District, Division of Quezon. After numerous statistical analyses, school heads are more competent in instructing and managing institutions by persistently expand their professional and personal development. Based on the findings, the instructional leadership and managerial competence of school managers were significantly influenced by their professional and personal development. The research study recommended that the school heads should always be updated in professional growth to enhance their holding power as school leaders. Nevertheless, enrolling in a graduate program is also one way on how to mold their headship. Inline to this, they will find out that creating different practices encourages teachers' professional and personal development which an opportunity for a good institutional atmosphere and competitive institution.

Keywords: Professional development, Personal development, Instructional leadership, Managerial competence